

CLASSIFICATION OF COST GROUPS AS INSTRUMENTS OF CONTROL PRODUCTION COSTS AND FINANCIAL RESULTS OF THE ORGANIZATION

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Abstract: The article presents a critical assessment of the principles of differentiation of various classification of cost groups used in the methods of analysis and planning of management decisions in the financial management system. The expediency of the existing diversity of classifications of costs, the choice of which will depend on the objectives and management level.

Keywords: Classification, costs, expenses, cost management.

Despite the international recognition of Uzbekistan's success and obtaining the "status of a country with a market economy and an investment credit rating" in the middle of this decade, the domestic economy faced long-term systemic challenges that reflect both global trends and internal development barriers. One of these challenges is the strengthening of global competition, covering the markets of goods and capital. In these conditions, support for entrepreneurial initiatives, increasing the financial stability and investment attractiveness of Russian companies, expanding their ability to operate in open global markets in conditions of fierce competition and overcoming the consequences of the financial crisis become important stimulating factors for ensuring economic development [2]. One of the main tasks of the companies' activities remains the maximization of income and profit, since profit is the main source of funds for further growth of economic potential [7]. The increase in profit at the enterprise can be achieved through cost

and cost management. Cost management is the process of influencing the subject of management with the help of commands, signals that are transmitted in different ways to the object of management, namely, the costs of the enterprise, in order to increase the efficiency of the organization. One of the important tools of cost management, along with the elements of accounting policy [5], is the use of an economically justified classification of costs. Cost classification is the grouping of costs by certain criteria. The main purpose of cost classification is to meet the information needs of users, that is, managers of different levels. The goals of cost classification are determined by the goals of the decisions made, the methods of achieving them, the degree of novelty, the validity period, and other characteristics. The efficiency of the decisions made and, ultimately, the welfare of the business entity will depend on the classification chosen by the managers [1]. First of all, depending on the level of consideration, production costs can be individual or socially necessary, valid, entrepreneurial, economic or accounting, which differ qualitatively, quantitatively and in structure [8]. For example, in tax accounting, expenses are classified for the purpose of calculating taxable profit, in financial accounting, information is generated about the amount of expenses as a whole for the enterprise, and in management accounting, cost classifications are determined based on the goals and objectives of management. For management, there is not enough data on the amount of costs in the entire organization. For management purposes, all costs should be divided into three target characteristics that are important for management: - determination of cost and financial result; - decision-making and planning; - control and regulation [1].

Classification of costs for management purposes [6]

Classification feature	Types of costs	Economic content
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Determination of cost and financial results		
By economic content	Cost elements	These include means of labor, objects of labor, and labor resources
	Cost items	Grouping of production costs by economic homogeneity, by purpose (material costs, deductions for social needs, labor costs, depreciation, etc.)
By the method of attribution to the cost of production	Straight lines	They can be directly included in the cost of specific types of products (works, services) Direct costs mainly include the costs of raw materials, basic materials, purchased semi-finished products, fuel and energy for technological purposes, and the remuneration of production workers with corresponding accruals
	Indirect	Related to the service and management of product production, sales of products, management of the organization as a whole
In relation to the production (technological) process	Main	Directly related to the technological process of manufacturing products, performing works, providing services (raw

		materials, depreciation, etc.)
	Invoices	They are formed in the course of servicing the production process, managing the activities of the organization's production units
By composition and degree of uniformity	Single-element (simple)	Homogeneous types of costs, such as, for example, wages, depreciation, etc.
	Comprehensive	They include several types of costs: as part of general economic expenses

Thus, one of the fundamental elements of a rational organization of cost management is an economically justified classification of costs. The multiplicity of types of costs and the principles of their classification is based on the large variety of resources used and their different roles in the formation of total production costs. The analyst's choice of the types of costs and methods of their calculation depends on the objectives of the analysis and the methods used to assess the efficiency of resource consumption [3, 4].

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